

Simultaneous quantitation of corticosteroid drugs with their specified impurities using liquid chromatography

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Abstract : A rapid stability proving HPLC method was developed and validated for the estimation of the corticosteroid drugs in combination drug product. The chromatographic separation of betamethasone acetate and betamethasone sodium phosphate and five specified impurities were achieved with Hypersil BDS phenyl column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) with mobile phase consisting of water and acetonitrile (67 : 38 v/v) using 1 mL/min flow rate (UV detection 254 nm). The method was validated as per ICH guidelines.

Keywords : HPLC, corticosteroids, validation, impurities.

Introduction

Celestone soluspan Injection is a sterile aqueous suspension containing two corticosteroid active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), namely Betamethasone Sodium Phosphate (BSP) and Betamethasone Acetate (BA) (Fig. 1). The clinically effective compound of the two APIs is their metabolite Betamethasone. BA and BSP are prodrugs used to treat corticosteroid responsive disorders¹. As a combination product they achieve their pharmacological effects through the immediate and slow release of Betamethasone^{2,3}.

A number of HPLC methods to analyze either BSP or BA in the pharmaceutical formulations or biological fluids are reported in the literature⁴⁻¹². However, there is very few HPLC method reported in the literature for simultaneous determination of the two APIs (BSP and BA) and estimation of their related compounds in any drug product formulations¹³. In pharmaceutical product development, impurity profiling plays an important role. The regulatory bodies such as US-FDA and EMA mandates to estimate the impurity present above 0.1% of the label claim for the active substance. The International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) has also provided a guidance document to monitor impurities present in new drug substances and new drug products¹⁴.

In this paper, we report a sensitive, rugged, and ro-

bust LC method for the estimation of BSP and BA along with their impurities/degradants in the drug product. The proposed method was validated according to ICH guidelines¹⁵.

Fig. 1

Materials and methods :

The standard drugs and samples were obtained from Strides Arcolab, Bangalore. Acetonitrile (HPLC grade) was purchased from Rankem and other reagents were of AR grade. All stock solutions were prepared using purified water. Purified HPLC grade water was obtained by reverse osmosis and filtration through a Milli-Q® system.

Instrumentation and condition :

Chromatographic separation was achieved by using a Agilent HPLC system, equipped with Photo Array detector (PDA) using Hypersil BDS phenyl column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size) column maintained at 30 °C. Isocratic elution was performed using water and acetonitrile (67 : 38 v/v) with flow rate 1.0 mL /min. 10 μL of sample was injected into the HPLC system. The absor-

bance was monitored at 270 nm. The mobile phase was filtered (0.45 µm Millipore filter) and degassed.

Preparation of stock and standard solutions :

A standard stock solution of BA and BSP at a concentration of 3 µg/mL was prepared with the diluent [mixture of water and acetonitrile (67 : 38 v/v)]. Accurately measured 2 mL of the well mixed injectable suspension is transferred into a 50 mL volumetric flask and made up to the volume with diluent.

Specificity and selectivity :

Forced degradation studies were performed in drug product to prove the sensitivity and stability of the proposed method. Forced degradation was carried at stress conditions of thermal (80 °C), UV light at 254 and 365 nm, hydrolysis (0.1 N HCl and 0.1 N NaOH) and oxidation (3% H₂O₂). Study period was 30 min for thermal, 8 h for UV light, 1 h for sunlight and 10 min for the hydrolysis and oxidation. Peak purity test was carried out by using PDA detector in stressed samples.

Validation :

The method was validated according to ICH and USP. The following validation parameters are addressed : Linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, selectivity, ruggedness and robustness.

Results and discussion

Optimization of chromatographic condition :

The main objective of the chromatographic method is to resolve BA and BSP from their specified impurities and other sample matrix. Isocratic system is preferred, as the peak shape and resolution were good. Hence it was decided to use isocratic programme. The HPLC separation was achieved at 30 °C. The monitoring wavelength was set at 270 nm in which both BA and BSP gave good response. The area ratio for two injections of BA and BSP were 0.99 respectively, hence it is concluded that the system suitability parameter meets the requirement of method validation as the results were within the limit, the diluent and placebo peaks are not interfered with BA and BSP and impurities peak. The developed HPLC method was found to be specific and suitable for quantification of BA and BSP in pharmaceutical dosage form.

Results of forced degradation study :

Forced degradation studies of the drug product were used for proving the stability indicating power of the developed analytical procedure. Peak purity of the samples under stress conditions were checked by using PDA detector. Degradation is observed in all stress conditions. However, degradation products generated are well separated from each other and BA and BSP peaks (Fig. 2). Hence the optimized HPLC method is considered has stability indicating (Table 1).

Method validation :

Precision :

The RSD values of BA and BSP were found to be within the limit of 2% for the method precision and intermediate precision study thereby conforming good precision. The precision of the impurity method was checked by injecting six individual preparation of betamethasone acetate and betamethasone sodium phosphate spiked with impurity. The RSD's of the related compounds were less than 5% and intermediate precision was less than 5% for all impurities confirming good reproducibility of the proposed method.

LOQ and LOD :

LOQ and LOD for impurities were established by calculating the scope and residual standard deviation from the linearity curve, using a series of known concentration of diluted solutions. Precision was performed at LOQ level by 6 replicate injections of all impurities and calculating the RSD of peak area of each impurities. The RSD of all impurities at the LOQ concentration was within 1.0% (Table 2).

Linearity :

50 to 150% of the analyte concentration of the standards was used to measure the linearity. Linearity test solutions for impurity method were prepared by diluting the impurity stock solution to the required concentrations ranging from the LOQ to 300% impurity specification level of LOQ. To establish the linearity, solutions were tested in triplicate. Peak area versus concentration data were subjected to least square linear regression analysis. The correlation coefficients were calculated from the

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Fig. 2

Table 1. Summary of forced degradation results

Condition	% Assay of betamethasone acetate	% Assay of betamethasone sodium phosphate
As such	99.94	99.88
Sun light	99.98	99.79
UV light	99.94	99.82
Thermal	99.96	99.88
Neutral	99.95	99.93
0.1 N HCl	99.98	99.89
0.1 N NaOH	99.89	99.84
30% H ₂ O ₂	99.96	99.88

Table 2. LOD and LOQ results

Compound	LOD (ppm)	LOD (%)	LOQ (ppm)	LOQ (%)
Betamethasone acetate	0.0597	0.0720	0.1343	0.1610
Betamethasone sodium phosphate	0.0467	0.0560	0.1246	0.1500
Betamethasone-17-acetate	0.0319	0.0380	0.0797	0.0960
Impurity-A	0.0473	0.0570	0.1260	0.1510
Impurity-B	0.0475	0.0570	0.1267	0.1520
Impurity-C	0.0315	0.0380	0.1260	0.1510
Impurity-D	0.0481	0.058	0.1121	0.1350

calibration graph. The linearity plot for the drug substances and impurities were obtained over the ranges tested (Table 3).

Compound	Regression parameters (n = 3)	
	Equation of regression line	R ² value
Betamethasone acetate	y = 17.021x + 0.073	0.997
Betamethasone sodium phosphate	y = 12.709x + 0.168	0.999
Betamethasone-17-acetate	y = 16.153x + 0.257	0.999
Impurity-A	y = 17.514x + 1.016	0.999
Impurity-B	y = 16.344x + 0.212	0.998
Impurity-C	y = 14.220x - 0.003	0.996
Impurity-D	y = 23.468x + 0.185	0.999

Accuracy :

The recovery studies were carried out by spiking the standard solution of BA and BSP into the placebo matrix. The samples were analysed in triplicate at each level as per the analytical procedure. From the result percentage recovery were calculated. The mean recovery at each level was between 90.0% and 110.0% and hence the accuracy results were found satisfactory.

Robustness :

The robustness of the method was determined by altering the experimental conditions to analyze test and sample solutions. The flow rate was altered by ± 0.2 mL/min i.e. 0.8 mL/min. Column temperature by ± 5 °C i.e. 25 °C and 35 °C and $\pm 2\%$ change in organic solvent composition in mobile phase. The RSD of standard was within 1.0%. The alterations did not affect the system suitability parameters for all conditions.

Sample analysis :

The method was applied for the determination of BA and BSP in sample. The proposed method was confirmed by six replicate estimations of pharmaceutical dosage forms. Good recovery was achieved (98 and 102%) and the recovery percentage was in good agreement with the label claims. The impurity level were determined and found to be within the limit.

Conclusions

The RP-HPLC method for the determination of BA and BSP is a simple, precise and stability indicating. The developed method can be suitably applied in the routine quality analysis of bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage form.

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